

Photonic Advances in Time and Frequency Metrology: Frequency Combs

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Abstract: Frequency combs are now the dominate tool in high-precision, high-accuracy optical time and frequency metrology. I will review their basic behavior, noise properties, design, and discuss a few applications currently pursued at NIST.

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Frequency combs have become single most important tool in optical timing and frequency metrology^{1,2}. In fact, the number of applications of frequency combs is large and growing, ranging from supporting optical clocks, to time/frequency metrology, to microwave generation, to precision molecular spectroscopy and beyond^{3,4}. I will discuss the basic components to a frequency comb and different simple models for describing the frequency comb behavior. I will then discuss some of the applications of frequency combs to precision time and frequency metrology including direct comparisons of optical clocks, time-frequency distribution over fiber and free-space, and microwave generation.

Fig. 1: A frequency comb is a stabilized laser system that provides a broadband optical output that is comprised of discrete spectral lines, each at a precisely known optical frequency with respect to an underlying clock. In addition, and of importance for sensing applications, this output is contained in a collimated laser beam with a single spatial mode.

The usefulness of a frequency comb derives from a number of features, which are partially captured in Figure 1. It is often described as a spectral ruler, providing comb teeth at precisely known optical frequencies with respect to an underlying clock. In the frequency-domain picture, the output is a comb of teeth at the well-defined optical frequencies of $f_n = f_0 + nf_r$, where n is the integer comb tooth number, f_0 is the offset frequency, and f_r is the repetition frequency. This description is particularly well-suited to describe the function of the comb in optical clock comparisons, where it allows a coherent connection between to highly precise optical oscillators. However, in other cases, it is useful to consider the comb from a different perspective. In particular, this basic equation is not always best suited to explain the different noise processes that can affect the comb performance. Also, for some applications, the time-domain pictures is more informative, where the output of the frequency comb comprises a series of perfectly spaced optical pulses with well-defined carrier phase progression. Depending on the experiment, either the time-domain or frequency-domain pictures can be most useful.

Although the performance of frequency combs continues to advance, the basic design of a frequency comb is fairly consistent across multiple platform (with the exception of the emerging area of microresonator combs⁵), and is shown in Figure 2. Some confusion can arise though

since the term frequency comb is used quite generally now to include both “free-running” femtosecond lasers and fully stabilized, highly coherent systems. For many measurements, the looser free-running combs are more than adequate but the most precise time-frequency metrology require tightly phase-locked systems. Ultimately, even the best comb is limited by the optical clock to which it is stabilized. I will discuss the different methods of stabilizing a frequency comb and some of the most recent compact portable designs.

The applications of combs are surprisingly broad; essentially any laser-based sensing system can benefit from the insertion of a frequency comb to provide higher stability or accuracy. The most obvious application of frequency combs is to support the comparison and dissemination of the output from state-of-the-art optical clocks or oscillators, which have reached remarkable levels of stability and accuracy^{6–9}. In that case, the frequency comb serves a critical role in comparisons of two co-located optical clocks, or future comparisons of remote clocks via either a fiber-optic links¹⁰ or a free-space links¹¹. Frequency combs can also be used to effectively downconvert the high stability of these optical oscillators to microwave frequencies¹². While these applications require the highest performance combs, many other applications benefit from combs even at lower levels of precision including range measurements and spectroscopy. I will touch on a variety of these different applications with an emphasis on the role of the frequency comb.

Figure 1. Basic schematic of a fiber laser frequency comb. The femtosecond fiber laser output is amplified and spectrally broadened in highly nonlinear fiber (HNLF). The offset frequency is phase-locked to a microwave reference. The remaining degree of freedom of the comb can be stabilized through (1) phase-locking the repetition rate to a microwave reference or (2) phase-locking one tooth of the comb to an optical reference (shown in gray). Solid lines represent fiber optic paths and dashed lines represent electronic signals.

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